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Abstract

The presented article is devoted to an analysis of research on the phenomenon of double modality in English within world linguistics, examined in terms of its geographical distribution and scientific directions. It is known that double modality is one of the relatively rare and underexplored areas in global linguistics; nevertheless, this phenomenon has been studied within various theoretical frameworks. In particular, the more frequent use of double modality in non-standard English dialects has drawn linguists' attention to this field. Research conducted under the terms "double modality," "double modals," and "multiple modals" has mainly developed in three directions: dialect syntax within the study of World Englishes, semantic and pragmatic analysis, as well as corpus-based research.

The aim of the article is to identify the geographical distribution and the main research centers of studies devoted to the phenomenon of double modality, to systematize the research carried out in this field, and to outline its principal directions. During the study, scientific articles, monographs, and corpus-based research published in various countries were comparatively analyzed. In fact, the main purpose of writing this article is to investigate linguists who conduct research on this topic, to examine the classical and fundamental works produced by them, and to review dialectal studies. One of the key objectives is also to determine the use of double modality in Standard English and to identify which linguists have studied it, since the investigation of double modality in Standard English, alongside non-standard English, is considered one of the central issues in linguistics and is analyzed as such. Undoubtedly, examining when research on this topic began is also one of the essential aspects of the study.

Keywords: double modality, double modals, modality, dialect syntax, standard English, non-standard English, corpus research.

Introduction

Modality in linguistics is regarded as one of the key grammatical and semantic categories through which a speaker expresses their attitude toward a proposition, including such meanings as probability, necessity, obligation, and possibility. In the English language, modality is characterized by a wide range of lexical and grammatical means of expression and, in comparison with many other languages, is particularly associated with the extensive use of modal verbs. One of the distinctive features of English is the possibility for two or more modal elements to co-occur within a single sentence. This linguistic phenomenon is commonly referred to as *double modality* or *double modals* in the linguistic literature. (Nuriyeva, 2024)

The study of double modality dates back to the 1970s and has since attracted increasing attention from linguists worldwide. It has been examined within several major areas of linguistic inquiry, including grammar, semantics, pragmatics, and, more recently, corpus linguistics and sociolinguistics. Double modality may be considered an integral component of the broader category of modality, as it reflects the speaker's ability to encode multiple layers of modal meaning within a single syntagmatic structure. When expressing an attitude toward an action, state, or situation, speakers may employ not only one but sometimes two or even three modal elements, thereby creating complex modal constructions that convey nuanced meanings and subtle distinctions. (Nuriyeva, 2025)

Such constructions often serve to intensify or refine the speaker's stance, allowing for the simultaneous expression of different shades of meaning, such as pos-

sibility combined with obligation or probability combined with intention. In this respect, double modality contributes to the expressive richness of language and reflects the dynamic nature of actual language use. At the same time, it should be noted that the majority of traditional studies on modality have focused primarily on single modal elements—such as modal verbs (*may, might, can, could, must, should, shall, would, will, dare*) or modal adverbs (*perhaps, probably, certainly*). These elements have often been analyzed in isolation, typically at the sentence level, without sufficient attention to their interaction within more complex modal structures. (Nuriyeva, 2024).

In contrast, naturally occurring discourse demonstrates that modal expressions frequently interact and combine, giving rise to layered or multiple modality. This is particularly evident in non-standard varieties of English, where double modal constructions such as *might could, may might, might should, and used to could* are more commonly attested. However, recent research suggests that elements of double modality may also be observed in more formal or standard varieties of English, although often in less prototypical or more structurally complex forms. (Hasty, 2012).

Within this context, the present study aims to contribute to the ongoing discussion by examining the phenomenon of double modality from a broader, global perspective. By focusing on the geographical distribution and main research directions in world linguistics, the article seeks to systematize existing studies, identify key research centers, and highlight the main theoretical and methodological approaches that have shaped the development of this field. Such an approach allows not only for a better understanding of the current state of

research on double modality but also for the identification of gaps and perspectives for future investigation.

In contrast, actual language use in discourse reveals more complex modal patterns; among these are constructions in which two modal elements occur together in combination. This linguistic phenomenon, primarily found in non-standard varieties of English, is known as *double modality*. (Di Paolo, 1989).

Double modals are particularly widespread in non-standard English dialects, especially in the southern dialects of the United States and in certain regional varieties of English. These constructions are expressed through forms such as *might could*, *may might*, *might should*, *used to could*, and others, enabling speakers to convey multiple modal meanings—such as probability, possibility, and necessity—simultaneously. (Mishoe, M., & Montgomery, M., 1994)

Although the phenomenon of double modality has long been regarded in linguistic literature as a peripheral and dialect-specific feature, interest in this area has increased significantly in recent decades. Contemporary research has shifted toward examining double modals not only from the perspective of dialect syntax but also within semantic, pragmatic, and corpus-based frameworks.

The aim of the present article is to identify the geographical distribution of research on double modality within world linguistics, to systematize the main research centers in this field, and to outline its principal directions. To achieve this, scientific articles, monographs, and corpus-based studies published in various countries have been comparatively analyzed.

It should also be noted that in the past decade, Azerbaijani linguistics has shown growing interest in this topic. S. T. Nuriyeva has published numerous articles devoted to the study of double modality.

Theoretical background

The Geographical Map of the Study of Double Modality in World Linguistics

The study of the phenomenon of double modality has primarily developed within the academic environments of English-speaking countries. In particular, the United States is considered one of the main centers of research in this field.

American linguists have mainly focused on the syntactic and semantic features of double modals used in the southern dialects of the country, analyzing the structure and functions of these constructions from the perspective of dialect syntax. For example, the linguist Athelstan Spilhaus has investigated double modality in Southern American dialects. (Hasty, J. D. 2012). Michael Montgomery has studied “regional dialects of America and double modality,” Lisa Green has examined “African American English and modal structures,” while the American linguist Douglas Biber has made a significant contribution to the study of corpus-based grammar. In addition, Walt Wolfram has explored double modality within the framework of “dialectology and non-standard syntax. Walt Wolfram’s treatment of double modality is primarily reflected in his works *Appalachian Speech* (1976) and *American English: Dialects and Variation* (1998/2016). In these studies, he analyzes double modal constructions such as *might could* and *might should* as systematic grammatical features

characteristic of Southern American and Appalachian dialects, emphasizing their role in expressing nuanced meanings related to possibility, ability, and speaker stance. A major strength of Wolfram’s approach lies in his rejection of the view that such forms are “incorrect”; instead, he interprets double modality as a sociolinguistically valid and functionally meaningful structure, thereby contributing to a more objective and inclusive understanding of non-standard dialects. However, certain limitations can also be identified. His analysis is largely restricted to dialectal data and does not fully explore the functional-semantic potential of double modality within Standard English or written discourse. Furthermore, the semantic distinctions between different double modal combinations are not always systematically elaborated. Overall, while Wolfram’s work provides a solid empirical and sociolinguistic foundation for the study of double modality, it also highlights the need for further investigation within broader theoretical and discourse-oriented frameworks (Wolfram & Christian, 1976; Wolfram, 1998/2016).

Research conducted in the United Kingdom, in contrast, has been more closely associated with dialectological and historical perspectives. British linguists have examined the historical development of double modals and their preservation in certain regional dialects. The research focus of Peter Trudgill has centered on British dialectology and regional varieties of English. Another British scholar, Jenny Cheshire, has investigated double modality within the framework of sociolinguistics and dialect syntax in the United Kingdom.

Among the studies carried out in the UK, two additional researchers occupy a prominent place: Joan Beal and David Britain. Joan Beal has focused on the dialects of Northern England, while David Britain has conducted research on regional variation and dialect syntax in British English. Furthermore, British scholars Bas Aarts, in his work on contemporary English grammar, and Geoffrey Leech, in his research on corpus linguistics and grammar, have contributed significantly to the study of modality as a broader category. (Aarts, 1998).

Since the 1980s, several linguists have played a key role in investigating modality from different theoretical perspectives, and their works have been fundamental for a deeper understanding of the phenomenon of double modality. F. R. Palmer’s *Mood and Modality* (Palmer, 1986, 2001) is considered one of the foundational works in modality theory. Jennifer Coates’s *The Semantics of Modal Auxiliaries* (1983) explores the semantics and combinations of modal verbs. Rodney Huddleston and Geoffrey Pullum, in *The Cambridge Grammar of the English Language* (2002), provide a comprehensive and detailed description of modal and semi-modal structures. (Huddleston, & Pullum, 2002).

Among German linguists, Bernd Kortmann has conducted research on World Englishes and syntactic variation, while Edgar W. Schneider has focused on grammatical variation within the framework of World Englishes. Angelika Kratzer, in her work *Modality* (1991), has established a profound theoretical foundation for the study of modal meaning, including double

and multiple modality. Jan Nuyts, in *Epistemic Modality, Language, and Conceptualization* (2001), offers a systematic analysis of epistemic modality, thereby further enriching the theoretical basis for the study of double modality.

The Finnish linguist Terttu Nevalainen has also made a significant contribution to the study of double modality. In her work on historical corpora and the development of the English language, she examines modality from a historical perspective, giving particular attention to its evolution over time.

Research on double modality has also been carried out in countries such as Australia and Canada. These studies are generally situated within the broader framework of World Englishes and focus on determining whether double modality exists in different varieties of English, as well as on analyzing their functional characteristics from a comparative perspective.

In Azerbaijani linguistics, the analysis of double modality in English has also attracted increasing scholarly interest. S. T. Nuriyeva has conducted extensive research on this phenomenon, with particular emphasis on the use of double modality in Standard English. She has published numerous articles and conference papers on this topic, including the following works: *Double Modality as a Lexico-Grammatical Means of Expressing Future Tense in Modern English* (2019), *Inversion as a Means of Expressing Modality in Modern English* (2022), *New Approaches to Scientific Theoretical Ideas about the Part of Speech Called "Particle" in Modern English* (2024), *On the Comparative Analysis of the Category of Modality in English and Azerbaijani* (2023), *Componential Analysis of Double Modality* (2023), *From the History of the Study of Double Modality* (2024), *The Role of Periphrastic Modal Verbs in the Formation of Double Modality in Modern English* (2024), *Productive Means of Expressing Double Modality in Modern Standard English* (2025), *The Role of the Particle in the Formation of Double Modals in Standard English* (2025), *Ellipsis in the Syntax of Double Modality: A Syntactic Perspective* (2025), *Componential Analysis of Double Modality in Discourse*

(2025), *Double Modality Beyond Modals: The Role of Mood and Inversion in Expressing Layered Modality in English* (2025), and *The Analysis of Double Modality in Discourse* (2026), among others.

The studies conducted by the linguists mentioned above have made it possible to examine various aspects of the phenomenon of double modality, that is, the broader category of modality, including dialect syntax, semantic and pragmatic features, as well as its use in corpus-based research.

In recent decades, interest in this linguistic phenomenon has also increased among scholars in Asian countries. Linguists working in this region have primarily focused on explaining the phenomenon from theoretical and typological perspectives, as well as on conducting research based on corpus data. Among the prominent representatives of the Russian linguistic school, Viktor Vinogradov, in his work *On the Category of Modality*, provided a classical interpretation of the category of modality, which continues to serve as a foundational framework for its study (Vinogradov, V. V., 1975). Another Russian linguist, Aleksandr V. Bondarko, examined modality within the framework of functional grammar in his work *Functional Grammar and Modality*. (Bondarko, A. V., 1990). Similarly, Aleksey D. Shmelev, in *Modal Meanings and Their Interpretation*, investigated modality and issues of multiple interpretation in discourse (Shmelev, A. D., 2002).

In Turkish linguistics, Aslı Göksel and Celia Kerslake, in their work *Turkish: A Comprehensive Grammar* (Göksel, A., & Kerslake, C.2005), analyze multi-layered modal structures in the Turkish language. Chinese linguists, who represent an important branch of the broader Asian linguistic tradition, have also made significant contributions to the study of modality. In particular, C.-T. James Huang, in *Modal Structures in Chinese Syntax*, and Wei-Tien Dylan Tsai, in *Multiple Modality in Chinese*, have examined double modality from a syntactic perspective. (Huang, C.-T. J., 1998).

Global Distribution of Research on Double Modality in English Linguistics

The map illustrates the geographical distribution of research on double modality in English linguistics. The size of each marker corresponds to the relative volume and influence of research conducted in the respective country. Major centers of research activity, such as the United States and the United Kingdom, are represented by larger markers, while other regions indicate developing or specialized contributions. The visualization is based on a comparative analysis of published studies, monographs, and corpus-based research.

Note:

It should be noted that this geographical map is relative, as it has been developed based on our investigation and reflects the findings obtained from our study.

The Stated Facts from a Critical Viewpoint

Although there are many studies on double modality, some important problems can be observed. Most research is mainly descriptive and focuses on identifying double modal forms in different dialects, but it does not always explain clearly how and why these forms function. In addition, more attention has been given to non-standard dialects, while double modality in Standard English has not been studied enough. Another limitation is the lack of comparative research across different languages, which makes it difficult to understand this phenomenon in a broader linguistic context. Even though corpus-based studies are increasing, their methods and results are not always consistent. For this reason, it is necessary to use a more integrated approach that combines syntax, semantics, pragmatics, and cognitive analysis in order to better understand double modality as a complex linguistic phenomenon.

Conclusion

The category of modality expresses the speaker's attitude toward the proposition and is studied in linguistics from this perspective. Modality is a multifunctional

and structurally rich category. In English, it is expressed through a variety of lexical and grammatical means, and in some cases, the co-occurrence of two modal elements gives rise to double modality, which functions as a more complex and multi-layered means of expression.

Although double modality is more frequently observed in non-standard dialects of English, its semantic and pragmatic potential is not limited to the dialectal level. It enables the speaker to express multiple modal attitudes or shades of meaning simultaneously, thereby increasing the expressiveness of speech.

The geographical mapping of research on double modality demonstrates that this phenomenon was initially investigated within the framework of dialectological traditions in English-speaking countries. However, in recent years, it has attracted broader international scholarly interest. It has been established that the study of double modality began in the 1970s and has been actively pursued in countries such as the United States, the United Kingdom, Germany, Finland, Australia, Russia, and China.

It has also been observed that interest in double modality is growing within Azerbaijani linguistics, and research in this area contributes to the development of both theoretical and applied aspects of the field. In particular, studies focusing on the functional properties of double modality in Standard English are of significant importance.

Thus, double modality can be regarded as one of the increasingly prominent and relevant areas in modern linguistics, attracting attention within various theoretical frameworks. Future research should focus on the comparative analysis of this phenomenon across different languages, as well as on its discourse and cognitive dimensions.

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